

UNDERSTANDING AND MITIGATING SUPPLY CHAIN DISRUPTIONS

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This article presents a comprehensive analysis of supply chain disruptions and explores strategies to mitigate their impacts. It begins by emphasizing the critical role supply chains play in global trade and economic stability, the connection and interdependence between economic growth and international trade, highlighting their vulnerability to diverse disruptions such as pandemics, geopolitical tensions, technological challenges, and natural disasters.

Keywords: *supply chain, disruptions, COVID-19, global trade, resilience, diversification, sustainability, technology.*

ПОНИМАНИЕ И СМЯГЧЕНИЕ СБОЕВ В ЦЕПОЧКЕ ПОСТАВОК**Умаров Шермухаммад Бахром углы****Студент факультета МЭМ, УМЭД****Аннотация**

В этой статье представлен всесторонний анализ сбоев в цепочке поставок и рассматриваются стратегии смягчения их последствий. Она начинается с подчеркивания важнейшей роли цепочек поставок в глобальной торговле и экономической стабильности, связи и взаимозависимости между экономическим ростом и международной торговлей, подчеркивая их уязвимость к различным сбоям, таким как пандемии, геополитическая напряженность, технологические проблемы и стихийные бедствия.

Ключевые слова: *цепочка поставок, сбои, COVID-19, глобальная торговля, устойчивость, диверсификация, устойчивость, технологии.*

In our modern society, supply chains are one of the most important parts of international trade, that provides countries all over the world with access to global markets. These chains act as a connecting link between members of global trade and essential for economic stability, yet they are very vulnerable to different types of disruptions, be it natural disasters, political restrictions or tensions between countries, and even pandemic events, such as recent COVID-

19. This essay analyzes and explores the nature of such supply chains, their fragility and examines strategies to enhance resilience and adaptability.

Remembering the effect of COVID-19 pandemic on the situation in the world, we can for sure claim that every country over the world underwent through isolation from each other. And this insulating effect of pandemic had huge impact on international trade, by creating invisible barriers which slowed down the development of global market. Due to this, many companies from small businesses to big international corporations were closed down. One example is Trans States Airlines - a regional airline from Missouri, whose operations ceased on April 1, 2020 due to a shortage of pilot.ⁱAs countries imposed lockdowns to contain virus from spreading and exacerbating the situation, it's epicenter China, experienced biggest losses in trading sphere and significant production halts, as it appears to be the largest global market supplierⁱⁱ, serving as a primary source of manufacturing and raw materials for numerous industries.

Not moving far away from China, one of the most notable spheres that was hugely affected by pandemic was automotive manufacturing sector. A consequent shut downs of car spare-part factories in Wuhan, significant automotive hub, led to the occurrence of shortages of components like semiconductorsⁱⁱⁱ, which are critical for vehicle manufacturing. Obviously, this shortage got beyond the borders of China and caused in production delays and increased costs. Similarly, the electronics industry experienced severe shortages in components, exacerbated by increased demand for remote work and learning technologies.

From increased demand of remote work, we can move to the next connected issue - labor shortage, as COVID-19 resulted in restrictions of workforce mobility^{iv}. Logistics networks faced congestion as container ships sat idle due to a lack of dock space and personnel. Shipping costs skyrocketed as companies struggled to secure limited cargo space.

Overall, we can count the effects of COVID-19 pandemic for a long time, but it is not the only thing that somehow influences supply chain. The next situation which directly impacts international trade is fluctuation in political relationships. Geopolitical tensions have long posed several challenges to global trade, and US - China trade war is a good example for this. Started in 2018, this conflict resulted in introduction of tariffs^v on a various spectre of goods, which created uncertainty and led to soaring of operational costs for businesses involved in international trading network. Thus, companies were forced to obey newly implemented tariffs simultaneously mitigating its impact on their bottom lines.

This trade conflict made impacted companies accelerate their efforts to diversify their supply chains by establishing new manufacturing bases in Southeast Asia, Latin America and Africa. Such diversification not only reduces dependence on single market but also enhances the overall resilience by spreading the risks of conflict across bigger amount of markets. In addition to that, this conflict made countries to revise their trade policies and strengthen their markets in order to be prepared for future conflicts and geopolitical shocks.

As we see, regional instability and conflicts can violate the policies of supply chains, mainly for companies reliant on specific raw materials. Sanctions and trade restrictions undoubtedly lead to supply shortages, increased costs and operational challenges. One of the most influenced by such conflicts sector is energy sector, with gas and oil supplies being a target during conflicts between countries. The best example among recent events is Russia - Ukraine conflict. In response to American sanctions, Russia, being the biggest supplier in energy sector, limited export of oil, which in turn resulted in increasing of costs^{vi} for it and in addition to that, many European countries faced natural gas deficit which also was reason to rising price for gas. This consequence of events reasoned the increase of demand for electricity and eventually the price for it.

Obviously, it may seem that supply chain is mostly affected by negative situations in the world such as political conflicts or global virus spread. However, even technologies, that are meant to be the engine of progress may act as a barrier for development of supply chains. On the one hand, the rise of automation in factories and development of artificial intelligence significantly contributed in optimization of manufacturing processes, reducing costs and improving efficiency. The use of AI in assembly lines facilitated calculations and increased cost efficiency by reducing excess production. On the other hand, it increased dependence of manufacturers on technologies, which introduced new edges of vulnerability - cyberattacks, that has great impact on supply chains. The great example is ransomware attack on Colonial Pipelines^{vii} in 2021. The attackers gained access to the system by means of a compromised password for a disused VPN account. The account did not have multi-factor authentication enabled. The main target of hackers was to hack the billing system of the company. As a result, company had to shut down some operations to prevent further attacks. However, the billing system was already taken down, so in order to carry on their operations, company paid hackers around 4.4 million dollars in exchange for a decryption tool. Such incidents show that even in quickly modernizing world, entities still have vulnerabilities and should always be on alert. Despite these challenges, technologies remain as the main enabler of

advancement and supply chain resilience which just needs proper use. The great example is usage of AI which is highlighted further.

Another player that can disrupt the trade is nature. Natural disasters^{viii} appear to be a big threat for supply chains with climate change exacerbating the frequency and severity of these events. Obviously, hurricanes, floods, wildfires, and other extreme weather events can disrupt production, damage infrastructure, and sever transportation links, leading to significant economic losses. As a response to these events, companies are implementing sustainable practices such as said above - diversifying geographical locations of factories to mitigate consequences of natural disasters. Furthermore, adopting economical and ecological principles such as recycling, reusing and etc. may reduce overproducing and for sure, excess dependency on technologies, reducing operational costs in the end and open space for investing saved money in enhancing sustainability.

Continuously facing such problems, companies are increasingly reinforcing their focus on upgrading their stability and resilience to be always prepared for challenges. There are plenty of strategies that companies use to strengthen their positions in global market, and diversification of suppliers and increasing local production are key strategies highly being adopted nowadays. Also the shifts from Just-in-Time to Just-in-Case management and vice versa allows companies to maintain stocks of critically important components, providing a “shield” against unforeseen disruptions. Last, but not least aspect of international business that should be highly focused on is advanced analytics and preparation of predictive models of market. Deeply examining the situation in global market helps companies to be aware of possible threats, thus prepare appropriate strategy. It not only empowers the resilience of companies and supply chains of course, but reduces the chance of occurrence of uncertainty and economical stagnation.

Many corporations these days are already implementing these strategies and one example is Toyota - huge automotive manufacturer. In response to COVID-19, Toyota, having Just-in-Time management, increased the level of critical inventory and diversified its supplier base^{ix}, which helped the company to maintain its position and continue production despite such challenges.

Another example is world widely known Apple corporation which also invested heavily in diversification of supplement markets to avoid dependence on a single supplier. Furthermore, company uses 100% of recycled aluminum^x in its products, demonstrating the leadership in sustainable supply chain practices.

Company which practices technological advancement and makes progress is Unilever. This consumer goods company invested in technological analyzing tools and AI to predict the demand for goods and be ready for market threats. Its commitment to innovative development enabled Unilever to become more resilient and strengthen its supply chain.

As our world evolves and countries create strong relations, global activities as trade and goods supplement will need proper observation. Companies facing various challenges will be more resilient in the future as every challenge needs individual approach that can be found only through deep analysis of market and situation in general, which in turn, enables companies to be more creative and come up with different, more adaptable strategies. All in all, challenge is a significant engine of progress itself that creates opportunities for innovations and growth of companies. As global interconnection continues developing, companies will always have opportunity to build a successful supply chains and be adaptable to any changes and disruptions.

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